

THE ROLE OF PARENTS AND FAMILIES IN SUPPORTING AND PROMOTING THE USE OF TECHNOLOGY IN EDUCATION

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Abstract. *The article discusses the importance of building digital literacy skills in students, which includes not only the ability to use technology effectively but also the ability to think critically about digital media and to understand how to navigate online spaces safely and responsibly. The article highlights various ways in which parents can support technology use at home, such as providing access to educational apps and websites, setting up a designated study space, and engaging with their children about the ways technology can support learning. Additionally, the article emphasizes the importance of collaborative efforts between parents and teachers to create a culture of digital innovation and digital literacy in the classroom and at home.*

Keywords: *Parents, families, technology, education, digital literacy, educational apps, study space, collaborative efforts, COVID-19 pandemic, equitable access.*

Technology has become an integral part of modern education, with its potential to enhance student learning and engagement widely recognized. However, for technology to be truly effective in the classroom, it is essential for parents and families to play an active role in supporting and promoting its use. Beyond the classroom, technology plays an increasingly significant role in all aspects of society, and its impact will only continue to grow in the years to come. This underscores the importance of parental support for technology use in education, as it empowers children with the skills and knowledge needed to thrive in a rapidly evolving digital landscape. In this article, we will explore the critical role that parents and families play in supporting and promoting technology use in education, the benefits of such support, and ways to foster a culture of digital innovation and digital literacy in the home and school settings.

Encouraging children to use technology for educational purposes at home can have a significant impact on their academic performance and overall development. There are a variety of ways that parents can support technology use for educational purposes, including:

1. **Providing access to educational apps and websites:** Parents can help their children find and use educational apps and websites that align with their interests and learning goals. For example, children who are interested in science can use apps like NASA Kids Club or Science Buddies to explore scientific concepts in a fun and interactive way.

2. **Setting up a designated study space with technology:** Having a designated space for studying and using technology can help children stay focused and organized. Parents can set up a study space with a computer or tablet, and make sure that it is well-lit, comfortable, and free from distractions.

3. **Engaging with their children about technology:** Parents can also have conversations with their children about how technology can be used to support learning. For example, they can talk about how online research can help with homework assignments, or how online quizzes can help children prepare for exams.

In addition to these strategies, parents can also encourage their children to be creative and innovative with technology. This might involve using technology to create their own digital

media projects, such as videos, podcasts, or blogs. By engaging with technology in this way, children can develop important skills in critical thinking, problem-solving, and communication.

Digital literacy skills have become increasingly important in the 21st century, as technology has become ubiquitous in both personal and professional settings. Encouraging children to use technology for educational purposes at home can help them develop the digital literacy skills they need to succeed in today's world.

Digital literacy skills encompass a range of abilities, including the ability to use technology effectively, to critically evaluate information found online, and to navigate online spaces safely and responsibly. By engaging with technology in a purposeful and meaningful way, children can develop these skills over time.

One important aspect of digital literacy is the ability to use technology effectively. This includes skills such as typing, using software applications, and navigating the internet. By using technology for educational purposes, children can build their proficiency with these tools and become more comfortable and confident with technology overall.

Another key component of digital literacy is the ability to think critically about digital media. This involves evaluating the credibility and accuracy of information found online, and understanding how bias and misinformation can be present in digital media. By using technology to research and learn about a variety of topics, children can develop their critical thinking skills and become more discerning consumers of digital media.

Finally, digital literacy also includes the ability to navigate online spaces safely and responsibly. This includes understanding how to protect personal information online, how to identify and avoid online risks such as cyberbullying or scams, and how to engage in online communities in a respectful and appropriate manner. By using technology in a safe and responsible way, children can develop the skills they need to protect themselves and others online.

By encouraging children to use technology for educational purposes at home, parents can help to build their digital literacy skills, which are essential for success in today's world. By developing these skills early on, children can become more comfortable and confident with technology, and be better prepared for the digital demands of the future.

In addition to encouraging technology use at home, parents can also support teachers' efforts to incorporate technology in the classroom. This might involve communicating with teachers about how technology is being used in the classroom, attending school events focused on technology, and volunteering to help with technology-related projects or initiatives.

Providing guidance and supervision around technology use is also an important role that parents can play. While technology can be a powerful tool for learning, it is important for parents to ensure that their children are using technology safely and responsibly. This might involve setting appropriate limits on screen time, monitoring online activity, and talking to children about digital citizenship and online safety.

Finally, parents can also advocate for technology in schools by attending school board meetings, supporting technology-related ballot initiatives, and encouraging schools to invest in technology infrastructure and professional development for teachers.

In addition to the importance of parental support for technology use in education, there are several wider implications for society and the future workforce. As technology continues to rapidly evolve and become increasingly integrated into all aspects of life, digital literacy skills will become even more essential for success in a variety of fields.

Moreover, technology can help to level the playing field for students from disadvantaged backgrounds, providing access to educational resources and opportunities that may not otherwise be available. By promoting technology use in education, parents and families can help to bridge the digital divide and ensure that all students have the chance to succeed.

Additionally, the COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted the importance of technology in education, with remote learning becoming a necessity for many students around the world. This has further underscored the need for parents and families to support technology use in education and ensure that students have the skills and resources needed to succeed in a digital learning environment.

Overall, the role of parents and families in supporting and promoting technology use in education extends beyond the individual student and has wider implications for society as a whole. By working together with teachers and schools to create a culture of digital innovation and digital literacy, parents can help to prepare their children for success in the digital age and ensure a more equitable future for all students.

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